

E. Cavallari^a, V. Bitonto^a, C. Corcos^b, A. K. Ramar^b, R. Katz-Brull^c, A. Bifone^a

^aUniversity of Torino, Department of Molecular Biotechnology and Health Sciences, Torino, Italy; ^bCortecNet, Les Ulis, France; ^cHebrew University, Department of Radiology, Hadassah Medical Centre, Jerusalem, Israel

Introduction

Deuterated 2-deoxy-D-glucose (DDG) enables non-invasive imaging of glucose uptake using ^2H magnetic resonance techniques **without ionizing radiation**. As a **non-metabolizable glucose analogue**, DDG accumulates in tissues with high glucose demand, providing **FDG-like metabolic contrast** while allowing repeated and longitudinal examinations. In this study, we quantify in vivo cerebral DDG uptake in healthy mice, evaluate its temporal stability, and assess the influence of anaesthesia using localized ^2H -MRS at 7T.

Methods

In vitro characterization

Phantom experiments (DDG-d₂, DDG-d₄, and DDG-d₇ at 300 mM, pH 7.4, plus a water reference) enabled acquisition of ^2H -NMR spectra (Fig. 1), relaxation time measurements, and validation of the quantitative performance of the **CSI-SSFP** acquisition strategy (Montrazi et al., 2024) (Fig. 1 and 2).

In vivo uptake

DDG uptake in the healthy mouse brain was quantified in vivo using localized deuterium magnetic resonance spectroscopy (^2H -MRS) on a 7T MRI scanner. Measurements were performed following intravenous DDG administration (**0.5 g/kg**) in both awake and isoflurane-anaesthetized animals to assess the influence of anaesthesia on tracer accumulation. Time-resolved ^2H -MRS was used to determine **uptake kinetics and steady-state concentrations**, including longitudinal measurements up to 24 hours post-injection. DDG compounds with different degrees of deuteration (DDG-d₂, DDG-d₄, DDG-d₇) were compared to assess potential effects on uptake and kinetic behaviour. To benchmark DDG behaviour against the metabolic gold standard, parallel experiments were performed using [6,6- $^2\text{H}_2$]D-glucose.

Figure 1. Molecular structures showing DDG at the three deuteration levels, and MRS spectra acquired at 7T.

Results and Discussion

Figure 2. CSI-SSFP was acquired using the sequence optimized for in vivo experiments, demonstrating quantitative performance as shown by the CNR plot on the right ($R^2=0.994$).

In vitro characterization

All DDG compounds were characterized by NMR spectroscopy. T_1 values were approximately **100 ms** (298–310 K), with a slight increase at higher temperature and deuteration level. CSI of the phantom demonstrated that the multiple DDG resonances collapse into a **single observable peak**, confirming quantitative detection ($R^2 = 0.994$), **signal proportionality to concentration and number of deuterons**, and absence of interference from natural water ^2H .

In vivo uptake

Following intravenous administration, DDG accumulated in the healthy mouse brain, reaching steady-state concentrations of **~2 mM**, with **no detectable washout up to 24 h**.

Comparable steady-state concentrations were observed in awake and anaesthetized animals, indicating that **anaesthesia does not affect** the final extent of brain **accumulation**, although uptake kinetics were faster in awake mice.

No differences in uptake magnitude or kinetics were observed **among DDG-d₂, DDG-d₄, and DDG-d₇**. In contrast to [6,6- $^2\text{H}_2$]D-glucose, DDG administration did not produce an increase in HDO signal, confirming its non-metabolizable nature and stable intracellular trapping.

Figure 3. In vivo brain DDG distribution was visualized using CSI-SSFP at 7T. Following intravenous administration (2 g/kg), DDG-d₂ produced a robust brain signal with an estimated CNR of 32 (TR/TE = 15.5/1.2 ms; matrix 8x8; FOV 30x30 mm; slice thickness 12 mm; 64 spectral points; 1209 averages; acquisition time 16 min 32 s).

Figure 4. (a) ^2H -MRS-derived brain concentrations following administration of DDG with different degrees of deuteration and of [6,6- $^2\text{H}_2$]D-glucose, (b) zoom of graph (a), (c) time course of cerebral DDGs concentration following intravenous administration (0.5 g/kg) in healthy mice measured in awake and isoflurane-anaesthetized animals.

Conclusion

This study establishes DDG as a **stable and quantitative** probe of cerebral glucose uptake, showing **anaesthesia-independent accumulation** at the relatively high doses used here (relative to FDG) and prolonged signal persistence in the brain, supporting repeated and longitudinal metabolic imaging. These results provide a robust **radiation-free** preclinical foundation for extending **DDG-based MRI toward translational and clinical applications**, including studies in sensitive and paediatric populations.

Contact: eleonora.cavallari@unito.it

References

- De Feyter, Henk M., "Deuterium metabolic imaging – Back to the future", Journal of Magnetic Resonance, 2021, 326 106932
- Gao, Xiao, 'Deuterium Metabolic Imaging of the Brain Using 2-Deoxy-2-[2H2]-d-glucose: A Nonionizing [18F]FDG Alternative', JACS Au 2025, 5, 571–577
- Suzuki, Chie, 'Conscious rat PET imaging with soft immobilization for quantitation of brain functions: comprehensive assessment of anesthesia effects on cerebral blood flow and metabolism', EJNMMI Res., 2021, 11:46
- Montrazi et al., Sci. Adv. 10, eadm8600, 2024